

SynergyLegal: Legal and Technical Challenges around Data Rights

Game Instructions

Number of Players: Ideally 5 individual players- 4 players and 1 game master.

Intended Audience: General public with basic interest in online privacy and security wishing to learn more about data rights. Skills required are reasoning, affinity building and debating.

Timing and duration: One round takes around 16 minutes. The game provides enough material to play 21 rounds but players can opt for a shorter version of the game by not playing all the cards.

Components

Mission: A legal and/or technical challenge on online privacy and security that ordinary people can possibly face in real life. The missions come in a set of cards (21 in total) and players aim to make a convincing argument on how to handle and solve them to earn points.

Skill cards: These cards complement the Mission cards as they provide useful info about the relevant legislation or technical protocol. They assist the players in solving the Mission at stake. There are 8 skill cards for each Mission.

Board: Functions to add motivational drives to the game as well as further challenges towards the end. There's a colored box for each round to be played and some boxes offer the possibility of earning double points, skipping the mission which results in loss of points and towards the end, the challenge of less time to solve the Mission is introduced as players will have gained practice by then.

Score Chart: It keeps track of points earned during the game.

Correct Answers Sheet: Provides an accurate solution to each Mission. The Game Master relies on this sheet to give points to the players.

Glossary

Game Master: The Game Master draws the Mission cards from the deck, distributes the skill cards to players, keeps the time during game, checks the correct answers sheet and gives points to the players according to the accuracy of the solution they come up with for each Mission. They also fill in the Score Chart and make sure that the players comply with the game rules.

Trophies: Recognition or award for an outstanding result achieved. The trophies are awarded at the end of the game. Any player scoring 450 points and higher gets a gold trophy. Any player scoring 350 points and higher gets a silver trophy. Any player scoring 300 points and higher gets a bronze trophy. These score thresholds are for those who play all the cards (21 rounds).

Game Setup

1. Place the board on the table and place the two decks of cards in the middle: **Missions** and **Skill cards**. Each Mission is numbered and comes with a corresponding set of **eight skill cards**. Check the board to see if that round has specific incentives or challenges such as double

points, option of skipping the mission or less time to play. Each round is represented by a colored box on the board.

2. The Game Master draws a Mission card and places it on the table revealing the content or reading it aloud. She then distributes the complementary skill cards to the players (**2 skill cards per player**). The skill cards are to be viewed only by the players who possess them.
3. The players get 6 minutes to reflect on how to handle and solve the mission with support from the skill cards. The Game Master keeps the time.
4. Once the time is up, each player makes an argument on how to handle and solve the challenge at stake (Mission). They each have 2 minutes to do that unless the board displays '1 minute less' for that round. Make sure to check the board for each round. Again, the Game Master keeps the time.
5. Players **give a point out of 5 to each other** at the end of each round depending on how convincing and impressive the argument was. The **Game Master gives a point out of 10 to each player** at the end of each round depending on the accuracy of the solution they come up with. The Game Master relies on the Answers Sheet to determine accuracy.
6. The Game Master adds the points to the Score Chart and then starts the next round.

Game Premise and Goals

Players get points from their fellow players by making a convincing and impressive argument. This depends on their skills of reasoning, affinity building, debating and making connections. Players are assisted by the Skill Cards in the game which provide useful info relevant to the Mission to be tackled. Players also get points from the Game Master depending on the accuracy of the solution they come up with. The player who scores the most points in total wins the game. On top of that, any player scoring 450 and higher gets a gold trophy. Any player scoring 350 and higher gets a silver trophy. Any player scoring 300 and higher gets a bronze trophy at the end of the game.

Game Rules:

- Players are not allowed to reach for information other than the one that is already provided by the Skill card.
- Players don't reveal their Skill cards to other players.
- Players are not allowed to view the Answers Sheet till the end of the game. It is only for the Game Master's usage during the game.
- Players need to comply with the time restrictions.
- Players are supposed to think and read silently during the 6-minute reflection time.
- When the board offers the option of skipping the Mission (not playing) for a particular round, any player who skips the Mission loses 10 points.
- When the board offers double points for a particular round, each player's total point for that round (points from the GM + points from the fellow players) is multiplied with 2.
- When the board displays '1 minute less' for a particular round, the players have 1 minute less time of reflection and 1 minute less time of presenting their argument.
- The game provides enough material to play 21 rounds, but players can opt for a shorter version of the game by not playing all the cards. In that case, it is advised that they decide on the point thresholds for winning trophies before starting the game.